

WEBQUESTS: AN EDUCATIONAL SUPPORT TOOL IN PUBLIC AND NON PROFIT MARKETING

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ABSTRACT:

Nowadays higher education is going through a period of transformations because, among others, two reasons: the introduction of information and communication technologies and the construction of common spaces for higher education.

These facts will mean a significant change in the educational activity: teachers will become learning facilitators and students will play a more active role in the construction of their knowledge. For that reason, teachers must find mechanisms in order to facilitate this new learning perspective.

Taking all this in mind, this paper promotes the use of WebQuests as very useful tools either for students and teachers in the society of information, more specifically in the teaching-learning process in public and non profit marketing fields.

Key Words:

European Space for Higher Education (ESHE); educational innovation; educative technology; WebQuest; public and non profit marketing.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Those changes experienced in the last few years in the educational scope as well as those forthcoming changes derived from the processes of convergence in educational systems, especially in the higher education, make it necessary to consider the necessity of an adaptation of the means used in the teaching-learning process.

The new foreseen environment is characterized by the elimination of space-time barriers, which involves new horizons in the field of the education, by introducing a significant level of flexibility in the educational processes. In fact, the changing rate of the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) means a real challenge in the university scope, where incorporating the new technologies and making an efficient use of them must become a fundamental part of the quality parameters, moreover when taking into consideration that the reach of these technologies in the University can be extended to three fundamental scopes:

- a) teaching and research contents;
- b) the teaching model; and
- c) the organizational model.

From this perspective, the main objective of this paper is to describe the main circumstances involving changes that are happening in the higher education level, by pointing out those necessary adaptations to be made at the present education systems and, consequently, the necessity of looking for new tools that could be useful to face such transformations.

In following pages, this paper will aim to show the very real necessity of availability of new helpful educative tools designed in order to fit the new proposals impelled in these processes of convergence. Because of that reason, the following sections of the study will focus in the analysis and explanation of one of these tools: the one so called WebQuest. It is a technology based on the internet use that promotes the development of students' researching and reasoning abilities, according to the requirements that are proposed in the new teaching-learning process.

In this sense, the second section is devoted to discuss the origin of the WebQuest tool, which, even when being a relatively recent instrument, already shows quite a great diffusion inside the educational community. Next, in the third section, an analysis of the components of a WebQuest is made regarding those common sections that characterize this pedagogical instrument. These components are the foundations of the example that is developed in the fourth section: a WebQuest that could be applied in the public and non profit marketing fields.

2. ABOUT THE WEBQUEST'S ORIGIN:

The Internet has become a source for searching of information in all the scopes of life. Nowadays it is an essential tool in the educational scope, both for teachers and for students. Nevertheless, at most cases the Internet is to provide such an amount of data that it becomes into a clearly excessive quantity of information. This means that when aiming to find useful and pertinent information for our work we must filter it, which entails a high cost in terms of time.

Therefore, the WebQuest tool will try to minimize that problem, by avoiding the excessive consumption of time when searching for concrete pieces of information.

The WebQuest tool was created by Bernie Dodge, professor at the San Diego State University, in 1995¹. This professor faced the necessity of teaching a course on a software application without either suitable materials or budget; only a video player and some websites were available for him. His students had to decide on the chance of applying the program at their school and, at this purpose, Dodge grouped them so that they could value the pieces of information by themselves, and then develop a report on the suggestion or not, all on the basis of the information that was previously selected by Dodge himself, which was available in the Internet.

Additionally, within each group, every student had to analyze the information from a different perspective, so that the same report would reflect a diversity of points of view, all of them seeming to be useful when considering the implementation of the program. Therefore a new learning procedure arose: generating something innovative from previously selected Internet resources.

Later, Dodge developed an organized matrix on what he called WebQuest (1997). It consisted of several activities: displaying a situation, enumerating information sources, giving a task, and reaching a conclusion. His creator (1995) considered a WebQuest to be *“an inquiry/research oriented activity in which some or all of the information that students interact with comes from available resources in the Internet. A WebQuest is built around an engaging and double task in order to allow the students a good use of time, focusing more on making use than looking for the information, and getting students supported when analysing, synthesizing and valuating this information”*².

A WebQuest involves students in the construction of their own knowledge at the time that teachers become guides, thus one of main characteristics of this tool is that it results in active learning procedures. At this point, Adell Segura (2004) defines a WebQuest as being *“an activity that allows students to elicit higher order thinking of some kind; it is about doing something with information: synthesizing, analyzing, understanding, judging, transforming, valuing, among others”*.

Not considering its components at the moment, some common and desirable issues regarding a WebQuest are as follows:

1. *Teamworking*: Everyone in a group assumes responsibility for one part of the whole task to be developed, thus he or she depending on the other group members to turn analysed information into a final output.

2. *Previous information selection*: students are not to spend their time just searching for information. The intended purpose is that they use the information that their teacher has previously selected because he thinks it to be useful in order to achieve the final output.

¹ As it can be seen at [<http://edweb.sdsu.edu/people/bdodge/bdodge.html>] (accessed at 26/07/2004). However, there are a number of websites devoted to this topic. Among them, we can clearly underline that one to be considered as the *“official”* one and so called *“WebQuest Page”* at the Department of Educational Technology, updated by Bernie Dodge himself [<http://webquest.sdsu.edu/>] (accessed at 26/03/2005).

² Available at [http://webquest.sdsu.edu/about_webquests.html] (accessed at 26/07/2004).

3. *Creative topics*: students are to solve task with a plurality of alternative solutions. Moreover, when searching and discerning between such alternative choices, they will have to use their imagination as much as research procedures.

4. *Interdisciplinary*: involved tasks may refer only one subject or research matter or, most times, may relate to several disciplines at a time.

Therefore, it can be noticed that a WebQuest raises a learning based on co-operation. Hence it promotes positive interdependence between students, individual responsibility when doing their work, communicative abilities and skills, as well as consciousness on teamworking as a group.

2. WEBQUEST'S COMPONENTS:

A WebQuest is shaped by two interrelated documents:

- A document to be used by the students, consisting of objectives, tasks, resources, etc.
- A second document for other teachers' use (in case the WebQuest is published in Internet or when it is intended for several users), including a didactic guide with instructions of students' required profile and previous knowledge, curricular objectives, practical recommendations on the time that students are expected to spend in order to do a proper work, etc.

The document that is designed to be used by the students consists of several components, as it can be seen in the chart in Figure 1. The concrete content of everyone of these components can be summarized as shown in following subsections.

Figure 1. A WebQuest's components.

Source: Based on Spartanburg County School District Three (2005).

Introduction:

The *introduction* of a WebQuest consists of a series of considerations for the students about the working related topic. The teacher should depict in an attractive way the various activities to be developed, in order to attract the interest of the students. Therefore, a WebQuest introduction should be clear, brief, motivating and, at the same time, able to put on the students a challenge to face, a question or a problem to solve.

Figure 2 shows the introduction for the WebQuest by Rosa Isabel Roig³ and entitled “*WebQuest. Learning through Internet*” (Roig, 2003), which aims to show such a new tool. This concrete WebQuest will be used as a reference example when describing the other components of a WebQuest.

Figure 2. Introduction of a WebQuest: an example.

The screenshot shows a web page with a yellow header. On the left is the 'EduTIC' logo. In the center, it says 'tecnologías de la información y la comunicación'. On the right, there are links: 'EDUTIC WEBQUESTS | DIRECTORIO DE ENLACES | LISTADO DE WEBQUESTS | QUIENES SOMOS | PORTADA'. Below the header, there is a navigation bar with 'MI EDUTIC / Proyectos'. Underneath is a login form with 'Nombre de usuario:' and 'Contraseña:' fields, an 'Entrar' button, and a 'Registrar' link. Below the login form is another navigation bar with 'WEBQUEST. APRENDIZAJE A TRAVÉS DE INTERNET | Autor: Rosabel'. A secondary navigation bar contains tabs: 'DESCRIPCIÓN', 'INTRODUCCIÓN', 'TAREA', 'PROCESO', 'EVALUACIÓN', 'CONCLUSIÓN', 'ORIENTACIONES', 'ARCHIVOS'. The main content area has several questions in red: '¿Sabes qué es una WebQuest (WQ)?', '¿Para qué sirve una WQ?', '¿Qué tipo de recurso es para trabajar en el aula?', and '¿Los alumnos de la Universidad pueden aprender a través de WQ? ¿Y los alumnos de niveles educativos no universitarios: Secundaria, FP, Primaria, Infantil, etc.?'. It concludes with an invitation to explore the site. At the bottom, there are links for 'Condiciones de uso', 'FAQ's', and 'Aviso Legal', and a copyright notice: '©2003 EduTic. Todos los derechos reservados. Universidad de Alicante'.

Source: Roig (2003).

Task:

A *task* is related to the description of what the students will have to obtain at the end of the WebQuest. Concrete duties could be presented in several ways: solving a problem or mystery, defending a position, designing a product, analyzing a current matter, making a summary, handling a kind of artwork, writing a journalistic article, etc.

Therefore, Dodge himself (1999)⁴ suggested a task classification by considering twelve different groups, as shown in the chart included in Figure 3. Next, a brief comment on everyone of these groups is included.

³ Main researcher and co-ordinator for the research project “*EDUTIC: Developing Learning Competences for Educative Higher Diplomas (Teaching and Psychopedagogy) by Using Internet*”. The WebQuest entitled “*WebQuest. Learning through Internet*” is available through the website at [http://www.edutic.ua.es/].

⁴ Available at [http://webquest.sdsu.edu/taskonomy.html].

Figure 3. WebQuest taskonomy.

Source: Based on Dodge (1999).

a) *Self-knowledge tasks*: students should answer questions on themselves. Therefore, they obtain a greater knowledge on themselves through a guided exploration. Topics could be on ethics, art judgement, long term goals, etc.

b) *Scientific tasks*: activities included by this second category are namely raising hypothesis from understanding on information provided by different sources, testing concrete hypothesis arising in such sources, describing implications from concrete hypothesis, etc. aiming an approach to the scientific method.

c) *Judgement tasks*: in this kind of tasks students are asked to decide or value about certain topics, commonly by performing different roles to express their judgements. It is advisable providing valuation criteria, but always allowing students to develop their own ones.

d) *Design tasks*: undoubtedly the most popular WebQuest type. Students must conceive their own product by taking into consideration a previously established goal or concrete restrictions. Students' creativity must be encouraged and, at the same time, they must be able to develop a product that somebody really needs.

e) *Retelling tasks*: this is the suitable kind of WebQuest when aiming students to use Internet as a source of information. Students can reflect what they have learned in short reports or PowerPoint presentations. It must be underlined that teachers should help the students to acquire skills for summarizing and composing and, at the same time, to be able to distinguish between the vocabulary they use and read.

f) *Journalistic tasks*: when involved in this kind of tasks students are requested to perform as press reporters; they must compile and organize facts by using usual formats for articles and news. Students are expected to understand concrete facts to a greater extent by considering different versions on them, and then they should try to avoid own bias.

g) *Consensus reaching tasks*: if facing this kind of tasks, students are expected to fit, as much as possible, their different opinions on a concrete topic. They must look for real opinions outside the classroom and analyze diverse resources, and then finally speak to a specific –either real or simulate– audience.

h) *Compilation tasks*: in this case students are to collect pieces of information from diverse sources and shape them into a common single format. Such a kind of tasks are useful at developing students' selection and organization abilities. It is advisable to use information resources in different formats and evaluating the consistence of the final work.

i) *Persuasion tasks*: here students should try to argue on a series of ideas in front of an external audience in order to convince them about a concrete issue (i.e. a trial, a group of citizens, the city council of a municipality, etc.).

j) *Analytical tasks*: this time students must observe one or more issues or aspects looking for similarities and differences between them, additionally to the implications that these entail. Thus, students could find causal relationships between considered aspects.

k) *Mystery tasks*: teachers must design a riddle to be solved by researching at several sources, aiming students to gather and then assimilate the information, meanwhile ruling out false hints. Undoubtedly, these tasks are the most attractive from the students' view.

l) *Creative production tasks*: students should produce something according to certain specifications (i.e. a play, a game, a song, etc.). Restrictions play an important role by here, as far as they are the key for the product to be developed. Teachers must decide about the concrete format to be used, length, use of a certain artistic style, etc.

Figure 4 shows, as an example, that task for students to make when developing the so called "WebQuest. Learning through Internet". It is a compilation task in which students are expected to make a file synthesizing proposed questions.

Figure 4. Task of a WebQuest: an example.

Edutic tecnologías de la información y la comunicación

EDUTIC WEBQUESTS | DIRECTORIO DE ENLACES | LISTADO DE WEBQUESTS | QUIENES SOMOS | PORTADA

// MI EDUTIC / Proyectos

Nombre de usuario: Contraseña: [Regístrate](#) | Recuerda no revelar tu clave

// WEBQUEST / Contenido

WEBQUEST. APRENDIZAJE A TRAVÉS DE INTERNET | Autor: Rosabel

DESCRIPCIÓN | INTRODUCCIÓN | TAREA | PROCESO | EVALUACIÓN | CONCLUSIÓN | ORIENTACIONES | ARCHIVOS

Para comprender mejor los contenidos que vamos a trabajar os proponemos como tarea que, al finalizar esta WQ, elaboréis un pequeño dossier o trabajo que resuma las cuestiones que abordaremos. El índice de este trabajo será:

1. Definición personal de WebQuest (según tus palabras).
2. Partes de una WebQuest (sólo citarlas).
3. Breve descripción de cada parte de la WebQuest (según tus palabras).
4. 2 ejemplos de WebQuests en Internet (Indicar dirección electrónica y breve descripción)

ALGO IMPORTANTE es que indiquéis cuánto tiempo habéis estado navegando por Internet buscando y leyendo información sobre cada aspecto:

- ♦ N° de horas dedicadas al concepto y parte de una WQ
- ♦ N° de horas dedicadas a ver ejemplos de WQ

El formato del dossier puede ser:

Source: Roig (2003).

Process:

Intended purpose of the third component of a WebQuest, the *process*, is to explain students when, how and what they should do, additionally to give an explanation on resources and support they could use in order to achieve expected goals.

At this point, students will face making different tasks and subtasks, for what they will be provided by supports to use in order to receive and transform the required information, thus finally coming into the design of a final product. Usual supports could be flow charts, conceptual maps and table-summaries. Students could be also supported by providing them with a check-list in which significant questions or issues at analyzing information are included.

When designing a WebQuest process it is necessary to take into consideration two different aspects:

- Sociodemographics on students (age, previous experience, knowledge, etc.).
- The nature of the selected issue (in case it would be a controversial issue or usually under discussion, etc.).

Considerations are significant at one or another extent when designing the process. Thus, and for example, in case of students are mature enough, then they could manage the work by themselves, and they will not require the presence of the teacher at every time.

Figure 5 shows a part of the process at the “*WebQuest. Learning through Internet*”, which is being used in this paper as a reference example for considering and analyzing a WebQuest’s components.

Figure 5. Process of a WebQuest: an example.

The screenshot shows a web page with a yellow header. On the left, there is a logo for 'EduTIC' and the text 'tecnologías de la información y la comunicación'. On the right, there are links: 'EDUTIC WEBQUESTS | DIRECTORIO DE ENLACES | LISTADO DE WEBQUESTS | QUIENES SOMOS | PORTADA'. Below the header, there is a navigation bar with the text '// MI EDUTIC / Proyectos' and a login form with fields for 'Nombre de usuario:' and 'Contraseña:', and a button labeled 'Entrar'. To the right of the login form are links for 'Regístrate' and 'Recuerda no revelar tu clave'. Below the login form, there is a section titled '// WEBQUEST / Contenido' with the text 'WEBQUEST. APRENDIZAJE A TRAVÉS DE INTERNET | Autor: Rosabel'. A horizontal navigation menu contains the following items: DESCRIPCIÓN, INTRODUCCIÓN, TAREA, PROCESO, EVALUACIÓN, CONCLUSIÓN, ORIENTACIONES, ARCHIVOS, and a printer icon. The main content area contains the following text: 'Antes de profundizar en el tema navega y observa la siguiente WQ sobre el agua: [LOS COLORES DEL AGUA](#) ¿Te has fijado bien en las características de esta WQ? Más adelante veremos más ejemplos de WQ. Ahora veamos algunas cuestiones importantes a través de los siguientes enlaces. A partir de ellos navega para encontrar y escribir la información requerida en la práctica:

1. [Concepto de WQ.](#)
- Si quieres más información entra en algunos de los [portales que hay sobre WQ.](#)
2. [Partes de una WQ.](#)
3. [Ejemplos de WebQuests.](#)

Source: Roig (2003).

Resources:

Resources are in the basis when intending an information research, which is a compulsory activity for students in order to develop the task. One of main WebQuest features is that one related to students are not expected to waste their time looking for and choosing between websites when aiming discern those really useful ones at their work purpose. Teachers should have previously navigated on the Internet and decided those websites considered to be suitable and relevant, according to the concrete task to make and the study topic.

Naturally, using a powerful browser is the best way when looking for websites. It should allow effective searches and, simultaneously, eliminate those less important sites. Once the interesting sites have been found, the teacher is to go deeper on their contents and structure, verifying that they would result really useful for developing the task (it wouldn't be worthwhile to consider some references in case they are to be totally ineffective).

Accessing all information and contents on a topic in the Internet is not always possible, because some of them could require a register or a previous payment, or because some materials are not fully available in the Web (as it could be the case of some books or manuals). However, the teacher may consider such a kind of references to be essential for students to understand the topic and develop the task in the WebQuest, and then, additionally to suggested websites, the teacher could include manuals, reviews and any other printed material available for students at a classroom, a library or a newspaper library. In this sense, either when initial purpose of WebQuest methodology intended to reduce waste of time when looking for information in the Internet, its real potential as an educative technology and pedagogical tool could be reinforced by using alternative resources, not even available in the Web.

Evaluation:

Students should know the way in which their performance will be evaluated before they begin their work, as this knowledge guides and motivates them. Hence, this concrete WebQuest component must be designed with a special accuracy, choosing evaluation criteria and telling the students about so that they will know what they are really expected to do. For example, if final product is a written presentation, then used vocabulary, syntax, structure of ideas, etc. could be considered for evaluation.

As usual when referring to any educative tool, the specific purpose of the *evaluation* in a WebQuest consists in measuring that knowledge that students acquire. Nevertheless, this time WebQuest evaluations don't use standardized tests as references, but demands that students will have to face in the real world.

At this purpose, it is usual considering one of two following techniques:

- A *portfolio* is a compilation of student's work samples, registers and test results, all aiming to evaluate either the development of the tasks and the achievement of intended objectives.

- A *rubric* is a score system that guides students' work according to previously established criteria. The teacher could decide to consider a rubric for everyone of WebQuest's sections or just a global one. Usual tendency is using rubrics, as portfolios are more long-term oriented.

Figure 6. Rubric design.

Source: Eduteka (2002c).

For example, a rubric design could be that one that Figure 6 shows (Eduteka, 2002b and 2002c).

On the other hand, Figure 7 shows the evaluation criteria at the case of the reference example “WebQuest. Learning through Internet”.

Conclusion:

In the *conclusion* section students are expected to reflect on what they have just learned. The intended purpose is encouraging them to go further with the research and to concrete the destination of the final output (to publish it in the Internet, to address it to appropriate authorities, etc.).

Figure 7. Evaluation of a WebQuest: an example.

EDUTIC WEBQUESTS | DIRECTORIO DE ENLACES | LISTADO DE WEBQUESTS | QUIENES SOMOS | PORTADA

// MI EDUTIC / Proyectos

Nombre de usuario: Contraseña: [Regístrate](#) | Recuerda no revelar tu clave

// WEBQUEST / Contenido

WEBQUEST. APRENDIZAJE A TRAVÉS DE INTERNET | Autor: Rosabel

DESCRIPCIÓN | INTRODUCCIÓN | TAREA | PROCESO | EVALUACIÓN | CONCLUSIÓN | ORIENTACIONES | ARCHIVOS

La evaluación de tu trabajo se basará en:

- Participación en los contextos de intercambio de informaciones, opiniones y valoraciones personales:**
 - foros,
 - listas de distribución,
 - correos electrónicos al profesor/a,
 - puestas en común en clase (para alumnos de Didáctica General)**
 - etc.
 - La valoración del dossier acerca de las WebQuests.
- Dossier elaborado:**
 - Importante que la información sea una elaboración propia y no un "copiado y pegado" de Internet.
 - La extensión no será excesiva: una o dos páginas.
 - Ortografía y gramática correcta.

Source: Roig (2003).

Final remarks:

A WebQuest seems undoubtedly to be an attractive way to get knowledge and learning. A WebQuest (March, 2000) should be:

1. *Real*: introduction and task should be devoted to make a reference to real world, so that students will find the WebQuest attractive, as far as it makes easier a feedback on real troubles or circumstances.

2. *Rich*: teachers should encourage students to be able of establishing relationships between knowledge on different topics, just in order to allow complementarities of ideas and generation of new viewpoints.

3. *Relevant*: topics and tasks should be decided on students' interest, so resulting in a major usefulness for they to get knowledge.

Regarding the benefits resulting from using a WebQuest, they come not only from students' but also from teachers' side. To be precise, students succeed to manage their own learning and assume a greater responsibility on it; they achieve what it is so called an "*structured cognitive scaffold*" or "*scaffolding*".

In a general sense, a scaffold is referred to an structure which is risen to support an edification or construction meanwhile it is built. In case of talking about a cognitive scaffold, a temporary structure is risen meanwhile students are acquiring new knowledge or abilities. The scaffold is made of competent people involved in other individual's learning process (McLoughlin, Winnpis and Oliver, 2000).

According to Dodge (2001), such a kind of scaffold is to be "*a temporary structure used to help learners act more skilled than they really are*". This author advises to use these structures at three precise steps in the WebQuest process: in the reception, transformation and production of information.

4. A WEBQUEST EXAMPLE ON PUBLIC AND NON PROFIT MARKETING:

According to statements in previous sections, a WebQuest is an useful Internet-based tool providing benefits either for teachers and students in quite a number of disciplines and different levels.

Following theoretical contents, and as an example, we have developed a WebQuest scheme, aiming the chance to use it in a teaching-learning process related to public and/or non profit marketing at higher (university) education level.

To be precise, this example is to be referred to the non-profit field, and a suggested title could be as follows:

"An Advertising Campaign for a Non Governmental Organization (NGO)"

In Diagram 1 it is included a tentative scheme for this WebQuest development, including some indications as a reference regarding everyone of different considered components (i.e. formerly mentioned sections of introduction, task, process and conclusion). Some additional considerations on available useful resources and the evaluation system are also included.

Diagram 1. A WebQuest proposal related to nonprofits.

WebQuest “An Advertising Campaign for a Non Governmental Organization (NGO)”

Introduction:

After finishing your studies, you are supposed to be employed in a marketing and advertising consulting. Some nonprofits (NGOs) have turned to your consulting in order to design their future social awareness campaigns. You are to design these campaigns!

Task:

Main task is related to designing a social awareness campaign, either for one or another (choose just one) of following organizations:

- a) *Médicos Sin Fronteras (Médecins Sans Frontières – Doctors Without Borders, MSF)*;
- b) *Aldeas Infantiles SOS (SOS-Kinderdorf International / SOS-Children’s Villages)*; o
- c) *Intermón Oxfam* (member of *Oxfam International*, 4 projects).

However, an previously to design the campaign, you need to know deeply the organization. Thus, the first task refers to make a report reflecting all issues considered to be important and characterizing selected organization.

Process:

You will be teamworking. Working groups will consist of three people. Every group shall choose one of three alternative organizations.

Firstly, you are to elaborate a detailed report on the selected organization. Maximum length for this report is 30 pages in *Word* format. It should include most relevant information on characteristic features of *Médicos Sin Fronteras*, *Aldeas Infantiles SOS* o *Intermón Oxfam*. Basic contents of your reports are to be:

- Origins.
- Main projects or activities.
- Countries where the organization is supporting projects or acting.
- Alternative ways of co-operation (ways of developing activities).

Once the report is concluded, you are supposed to know the organization deeply, and thus it is time to design the social awareness advertising campaign. Main intended purpose for this campaign is making people aware on the needs for their help. In the resources section you will find some useful information on advertising.

Your designed advertising campaign will be supported in three different mass media: press, television and radio.

In case of written press, it will be supported full page inside a magazine. Therefore, you must get a design for such as size.

On television a commercial of 60 seconds long as a maximum will be broadcasted.

Finally, on the radio the campaign will result into an 30 seconds long spot that you will have to record.

Continues ...

Diagram 1. A WebQuest proposal related to nonprofits (continuation).

Resources:

To search for information on organizations and make an entire report:

- *Médicos Sin Fronteras* website [<http://www.msf.es/>].
- *Aldeas Infantiles SOS* website [<http://www.aldeasinfantiles.es/>].
- *Intermón Oxfam* website [<http://www.intermonoxfam.org/>].

When studying key issues on advertising:

- On concepts and objectives of advertising:
 - [http://www.canalpublicidad.com/aula/aula_vision.asp?apuntes=swf/introduccion.swf&tipo=swf].
- On advertising creative processes:
 - Ortega, E. (2004): *La Comunicación Publicitaria*. Madrid: Pirámide (⇒ pp. 217-254).
- On making an advertising message:
 - García, M. (2001): *Las Claves de la Publicidad*. Madrid: Esic (⇒ pp. 237-262).
- A typology on advertising campaigns:
 - [<http://www1.universia.net/CatalogaXXI/pub/ir.asp?IdURL=125854&IDC=10010&IDP=ES&IDI=1>] (⇒ page 2, *Campaigns-Typology*).
- Examples of advertising campaigns:
 - [<http://www1.universia.net/CatalogaXXI/pub/ir.asp?IdURL=125854&IDC=10010&IDP=ES&IDI=1>] (⇒ page 2, *Advertising campaigns-Library*).

Evaluation:

The valuation of the report will be based on following criteria:

- Development of the required aspects.
- Use of vocabulary.
- Quality of written text.

On the other hand, the advertising campaign will be valued on following criteria:

- Respect of specified formats.
- Originality.
- A right election and adaptation of the format for publication inside a magazine.
- Quality of images and design of the commercial for television.
- Quality of sound of radio spot.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH:

Recent and current transformations occurred at higher education level will renew the teaching-learning process as it was conceived and developed at the twentieth century, as far as students will have a major autonomy when getting their knowledge, thus resulting in the end of a situation where teachers used to be like “owners” of this knowledge. Additionally, all the work done by the students (study hours to prepare exams, seminars, tutorials, etc.) will be taken into account in order to decide if they pass a subject. In other words, that is the educator will not be main focus any longer, but student will be.

What is more, expected new environment is characterized by the elimination of space-time barriers and, consequently, new ways of facing such changes are required. New Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) become essential tools in the future of education, especially when talking about higher education. Teachers and students will demand for new and improved ways facilitating exchange of information and communication, additionally to the fact that students will be allowed to perform a main role in their own learning process.

At this point, in this paper we have analyzed the role that a WebQuest tool may play as an instrument fulfilling all requirements, then showing an example on a concrete possible WebQuest application in the public and non profit marketing fields.

Therefore, we encourage the chance of application of these technologies for university teaching in a discipline or research field as previously stated of public and non profit marketing is, in which it is necessary to develop logic or simulation capacities, all by taking into consideration those contributions that a WebQuest may offer, aiming to facilitate an educative redesign according to new proposals on higher education.

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